

The Role and Significance of Activity Games in the Development of Children's Physical Qualities

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Abstract: The game process varies depending on the type of game, the most important thing is that the game is interesting for children, can make children happy and look forward to the start of this process more quickly. Should be carried out in the system. The article provides information on the role and importance of active games in the development of children's physical qualities.

Keywords: active games, fitness, children, physical qualities, quickness, agility, flexibility, general physical development.

INTRODUCTION

The most basic and vital movements: walking, running, jumping, hanging, pulling, throwing, balancing, etc. are the main source of the child's comprehensive development.

When teaching children the basics of movements, the coach solves educational and health-improving tasks along with teaching. In particular, from physical exercises: quickness, agility, flexibility, along with strengthening the muscles, it also develops the cardiovascular, respiratory and nervous systems.

Physiological and psychological readiness of six-year-old children to study and school is mainly manifested in what? A 6-year-old child has learned to move from a young age, so he will have little movement experience.

It is also known that the general physical development of 6-7-year-old children begins to occur hormonally.

In them, basic movement, cardiovascular, respiratory, internal secretion glands develop rapidly. Therefore, the following tasks are assigned to the school preparatory group: improving the children's walking and running skills throughout the year, that is, in some cases, walking with movement in a wide and free medical condition, easy uniform running. Being able to maintain the same set task while walking and running and being able to quickly change it again. To learn to run jumps and jump with proper footing.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

To develop different methods of accurate shooting at a target, to develop throws, to teach to perform the actions while hanging and scrambling to the same standard. To teach children to line up and re-line up in one place, to line up in a row, side by side, forming a circle, and to properly develop stature. As indicated in the educational program of physical education for kindergartens, the following basic movement exercises are taught on the didactic principle and are progressively complicated.

Action games with walking and running. Before going to school, children should master the basic movements of walking and running. they need to be able to keep their height and walk lightly.

"Flag". Children stand in a row (line up in a row) and then walk (run) to the corner of the square or room. The first child had a flag in his hand and shouted "Stop!" all the children stop at his words. The teacher calls one of the children, he takes the flag from the previous child, he goes to the front of the line and the march (run) continues.

When the children quickly learn to go to the front of the line, then it is possible to change the front of the line without stopping the movement of the line. When children are walking (running), it is permissible to put a flag on the top of the pole in the corner of the field or room, because when children walk and run, they learn to turn correctly in those corners. Later, there will be no need to put a flag on the pole, because the children will get used to walking and running around corners.

"Be alert!" Children are running in a line, each child may have a flag or a ball in his hand. At this moment, the teacher says the name of a child. Then the child picks up something in his hand. Then he says the name of another child, and when he raises something in his hand, the first child lowers the flag.

"High and low". Children line up one after the other, according to their height. They walk and run in this direction. The teacher puts the tall ones in front, and the short ones behind them, according to the order.

"Turn around!" Children walk (run) in a line. In this way, he goes somewhere (wall, tree, window) and turns back, the child leading the line leads the line. In the next turns, he teaches to change the direction and walk (run) by suddenly hitting a circle, playing a whistle or clapping.

In the next turns, the teacher says: "Turn!" or suddenly (by clapping or hitting a circle) can change walking, running.

"Trail of the snake". Balls (made of rags, cloth, filled with old cotton and sand) are placed in a circle on the field or floor at an interval of 40-50 cm. Children line up in a circle. According to the teacher's order, "Walk!" when they say, they walk in a circle. When they say "along your snake", they walk (run) around any stuffed balls. This exercise can also be performed to the sound of music or to the sound of a circle in the same rhythm.

"Circles". Circles with a circumference of 25-30 cm are placed on the field or along the length of the room at intervals of half a step. Children are told to place their foot in the center of the circle while walking. The advantage of this walking exercise is that it teaches you to step on your toes. After the walking exercise, the distance of the circles in it is changed. In return, children are taught to walk wider and "flyer".

"Hear the sound and do it!" One by one, children hold hands and walk (run) in pairs. When the teacher makes a sound (clapping, beating in a circle), they quickly lower their hands and continue to walk (run) side by side, not behind, without chasing each other. they walk (run) in pairs.

"One, two." Children line up, then line up again, two by one, in a row, in pairs, without holding hands, keeping a clear distance. As soon as the teacher says "One", the children walk again without stopping. When they say "two", they walk in pairs.

"Turn around!" It is permissible to teach children to turn around in pairs while standing in one place, it is done inwardly, that is, face to face.

"Gate!" Children walk (run) in pairs without holding hands. They stop when the teacher says "gates", hold each other's hands and raise them high. The last running couple passes under the "gate", goes forward and stands first. Again, all the children continue to walk. When the sound is heard again, forming a "gate", the partners go forward again.

"Walking in a dark house". After passing one corner of the room, the children line up. Then the teacher goes to the middle of the room

Come to a distance of 3-4 m and say to the children: "Look in my direction, close your eyes and say, 'Stop!' you will walk until he says." In other words, children walk a distance of 3-4 m as if they were walking in a dark house.

"The feet were beating." Children walk (run) in a line. The teacher looked at the children and said: "When you walk, cross your legs and walk longer!" he orders. The teacher himself must first show how to perform this exercise.

"Overcoming obstacles". In the hall, room or square, children line up side by side. The teacher tells them how to pass the obstacles if they have completed the exercise. When the children walk forward, they say, "Go over the hurdles with your knees high!" he says. Children do. "Get on the bus!" Running quickly across the field from side to side. The teacher looked at the children and said, "Come on, kids, the bus is waiting for you across the street, move quickly!" he orders.

"Spread!" (Run.) Children walk (run) spread out in a designated part of the field or room. The teacher's "Stop!" As soon as they hear the command (or the circle sound), the children stop. The main goal of the teacher is that children use as much space as possible without interfering with each other when walking.

"In water, on land." The exercises will be held as in the previous trip. Only when the teacher makes a sound and says "in the water", the children walk as if the water is running on their toes, when it is said "on the dry land", they walk on their heels.

"Don't touch!" A flag pole, a chair, a stuffed ball, a hoop, a keg, etc. are placed on each side of the room, the distance between them should be different. Children should walk between these objects without touching them.

"Swap places". A line is drawn through the middle of the room or diagonally. Children are divided into two groups, each of them settles in one or the other half of the room. The teacher says "Run!" when all the children start running in their own half of the court. At this time, as soon as the teacher hits the circle or says "change places", each group should try to quickly move from its platform to another platform.

Types of actions of students in action games. It consists of performing various specified exercise-tasks while walking and running: knowing how to pass between objects, collecting them, taking them from one place to another, etc.

"Who found what?" Small things are placed on each side of the room depending on the number of children. And the children run from one place to another between the objects.

The teacher tells the children: "When walking, do not bend your head forward, walk straight ahead, learn to give way to each other," then "Stop!" as soon as he says, all the children stop and lift whatever is close to their hands (a bowl, a bag) to the top.

"Experience". Children stand in a circle, each of them holding a colored flag. According to the teacher's instructions, each child puts his flag on the place where he is (on the floor, on the ground) and walks around the room or the field. But it is forbidden to enter the center of the circle. Then the teacher shouted: "One, two, three - run to the whole circle!" children run to their places and show their flags.

Types of actions of students in action games. These exercises are performed when walking and running over obstacles (jumping over, going under, jumping over), chasing, running without giving a handle to the chaser.

"Go through the barriers!" On one side of the room, the children are lined up. In the rest of the room, gymnastic sticks are placed crosswise on chairs. While walking, children must pass the first obstacle-stick without stopping the one coming from behind, pass under the second obstacle (a stick placed on the cross chairs) and pass the third stick, so They should walk 8 steps on their toes with their hands up, and another 8 steps on full heels. when the children have mastered this exercise, they can also run the exercise.

CONCLUSION

If the pedagogue knows the physical condition of the children well, in order to properly approach this process, he combines a strong child with a weak child, or a fast child with a slightly slower child in a team or a small group. In this case, the child's leadership activity increases, his enthusiasm increases, and in the next game he develops himself more and more.

When creating action games, the teacher should pay attention to the development of different games and different physical qualities. For example, during one training session, the focus should be on the development of speed and agility, while on the other training session, flexibility and strength should be developed. It is also possible to make changes to some subject of this game, which causes various creativity and ideas to arise in the students during the action games. When the teacher organizes a game based on different plots and events during the game, it becomes more interesting. This process develops the child's ability to continue playing and, in his case, his creative and aesthetic abilities.

No matter what kind of sport it is, teaching it through various movement games is the reason for the growth of physical qualities of children, especially in preschool and elementary school students, to improve their physical characteristics, and through this process, they show various abilities. ladi

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